

PERCEPTION AND THE LEVEL OF LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG BANK EMPLOYEES

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Abstract:

This study focused on the perception and level of life satisfaction among bank employees. Bankers are the most important group of professionals for our nation's economic growth. Today, most bankers are dissatisfied with their jobs. Job satisfactions of bank employees are good not only for themselves but for society as a whole. When the bankers are satisfied with their jobs, only then are they interested in providing service efficiently and effectively. The data used in this paper is primary in nature and was collected through a questionnaire from a sample of 180 teachers. The collected data were analyzed using the weighted average and weighted mean score tests.

Key Words: Life Satisfaction, Employees, Age, Area of Residence, Marital Status and Type of Family.

Introduction:

Life satisfaction is a measure of a person's well-being, assessed in terms of mood, relationship satisfaction, achieved goals, self-concepts, and one's self-perceived ability to cope with life. Life satisfaction involves a favorable attitude toward one's life rather than an assessment of current feelings. A satisfied life is better than a successful life. Because our success is measured by others. But our satisfaction is measured by our own soul, mind, and heart. Basically, a bank job is not an easy one; it is more stressful. Life satisfaction directly influences the job. So, this study focused on the life satisfaction of bankers.

Review of Literature:

Nikarika, U. V. Kiran (2014), in their study "Life satisfaction among bank employees". The purpose of this study was i. to determine the life satisfaction of bank employees. To assess the relationship between independent variables and various components of life satisfaction. The study has found that, job safety, salary of the employees, benefit given to employees and work experience influences the private bank employee's life satisfaction.

Parminder Walia (2014), in his study on "Work life balance of bank employees: A comparison". The present study focused on to compare the work life balance of employees working with public and private sector banks. Research have stated that public sector bank employees have a better work life balance and private sector bank employees have not better work life balance. Work arrangement, flexible location, leave arrangement, child care arrangement are the factors which highly influences their work-life balances.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the perception towards life satisfaction of bank employees.
- To identify the level of life satisfaction among the bank employees.

Need and Scope of the Study:

From the literature reviewed the lacuna was identified that family, financial assistance and self-management plays a vital role for life satisfaction of the employees. The present study is focused on the analyzing the life satisfaction of bank employees whose work culture is different to other type of employees. This study also aimed to analyze the level of life satisfaction among employees. The study can be further extended to educational institutions, hospitals and various private and public sectors also.

Limitations of the Study:

- This research was conducted only in and around pollachi area.
- The sample size was confined only to 180 respondents.
- Satisfaction level to environment factor may differ from person to person.

Research Methodology:

The research methodology employed for carrying out the study is explained in the following section.

Data:

The data required for the study is primary and secondary. Primary data were collected by issuing questionnaire to the respondent. The secondary data were collected through various books and websites. The design of the questionnaire is made in such a way that it considers self management, personal life, family and financial assistance of bank employees.

Data Collection Period:

Required data has been collected for the study within three months.

Sampling Procedure:

A sample of 180 employees working in various bank situated in pollachi town has been considered for the purpose of this study. Convenient sampling procedure has been followed to collect data.

Perception of Life Satisfaction:

The following table has been prepared on the basis of bank employees' opinions about life satisfaction. According to the result of various researches, only selected variables have been taken into account to know their opinion on life satisfaction.

S.No	Life Satisfaction Variables	SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total	Weighted Average Score
1	Good Health / Fitness	93	61	13	2	11	180	4.25
		(51.67%)	(34.17%)	(7.50%)	(0.83%)	(5.83%)	(100.00%)	
2	Home / Physical Environment	90	58	19	5	8	180	4.22
		(50.00%)	(32.50%)	(10.83%)	(2.50%)	(4.17%)	(100.00%)	
3	Partner Love and Relationship	94	55	11	9	11	180	4.19
		(52.50%)	(30.83%)	(5.83%)	(5.00%)	(5.83%)	(100.00%)	
4	Family, Friends and Social Relationships	94	54	15	9	8	180	4.22
		(52.50%)	(30.00%)	(8.33%)	(5.00%)	(4.17%)	(100.00%)	
5	Spouse work environment	77	56	22	13	12	180	3.95
		(42.50%)	(30.83%)	(12.50%)	(7.50%)	(6.67%)	(100.00%)	
6	Better Economic Level	80	80	12	2	6	180	4.23
		(44.17%)	(44.17%)	(6.67%)	(0.83%)	(4.17%)	(100.00%)	
7	Achieving Goals	68	76	29	4	3	180	4.12
		(37.50%)	(42.50%)	(15.83%)	(2.50%)	(1.67%)	(100.00%)	
8	Good Relationship with others	73	79	16	8	4	180	4.18
		(40.83%)	(44.17%)	(9.17%)	(4.17%)	(1.67%)	(100.00%)	
9	Social Status	80	88	7	2	3	180	4.33
		(44.17%)	(49.17)	(4.17%)	(0.83%)	(1.67%)	(100.00%)	
10	Spirituality	54	90	16	14	6	180	3.96
		(30.00%)	(50.00%)	9.17%	7.50	(3.33%)	(100.00%)	

The result from weighted average score shows that most of the respondent says that Good health, Home/Physical Environment, Partner Love and Relationship, Family, Friends and Social Relationships, a Better Economic Level, Achieving Goals, Good Relationship with others and Social Status are the variables that are highly determined factors of life satisfaction.

Level of Life Satisfaction:

Self-Management:

Bank employees often feel that they are living their lives with passion, joy, a positive attitude, gratitude, exciting dreams, hopes, and aspirations to look forward to, and clear goals. They are sometimes feeling in that they are hardly ever angry, to find positive ways to deal with stress, to think, plan, and schedule their day-to-day activities, to have sufficient time to take care of themselves, stay focused on their work, and be satisfied with their level of self-confidence and creativity.

Family:

Most of the bank employees often feel that they are happy with their family; they support their spouse morally and financially, are patient to hear their kids' conversations, and feel guilty when their family is not happy. Rarely feel that they spend sufficient time with their children's studies and having food with their family at least once a week.

Employee's Life Satisfaction – Mean Score:

S.No	Life Satisfaction Variables	Mean Score	Weighted Mean Score
Self - Management			
1	I live my life with Passion	4.06	3.83
2	I live my life with Joy	4.05	
3	I lead my life with a positive attitude	4.03	
4	I lead my life with gratitude	4.12	
5	I have exciting dreams, hopes and aspirations to look forward to	4.12	
6	I have clear goals	3.95	
7	I am hardly ever angry	3.51	
8	I find positive ways to deal with stress	3.80	
9	I have enough time to think, plan and to schedule my day to day activities	3.63	
10	I have sufficient time to take care of myself	3.46	
11	I stay focused on my work	3.83	
12	I find it easy to forgive others when	3.74	

S.No	Life Satisfaction Variables	Mean Score	Weighted Mean Score
	I have been hurt		
13	I am satisfied with my level of self confidence	3.92	
14	I feel I express my creativity	3.48	
Family			
16	I am happy with my family	3.96	3.26
17	I feel happy to support my spouse morally and financially	3.86	
18	My spouse equally supports me in my personal and career development	2.83	
19	I am happy with the family members support in my all activities	2.83	
20	I have patient to hear my kids' conversation with me	3.84	
21	I spend my time with my children	2.63	
22	I can concentrate on my children studies	2.55	
23	I am having food along with my family at least once in a day	2.73	
24	I feel guilty when my family is not happy	4.14	
Personal life			
25	I know that humor, laughter and playfulness are important parts of my daily life	4.18	4.04
26	I could balance between career and personal life	3.99	
27	I have strong faith which sustains me throughout my life	4.15	
28	I am satisfied with my ideal life as per my plan	4.07	
29	I know the purpose of my life	4.00	
30	I am aware and enjoy living in the moment	3.96	
31	I am satisfied with the separation of both my professional and personal life without any conflict	3.95	
32	My life is balanced physically, emotionally and spiritually	3.90	
Financial Assistance			
33	I am financially secure	3.86	3.86
34	I have clear financial goals	3.83	
35	I get stressed often due to my income level	3.76	
36	I know, I can solve my financial problems	3.96	
37	I can help my family to solve the problems that arise due to money	3.92	
38	Repayment of loans is easier for me through my good package	3.83	

Personal-Life:

Here, all employees frequently feel the way described under personal life variables.

Financial Assistance:

Employees often feel that they are financially secure, that they have clear financial goals, that they get stressed about their income level, that they can solve family financial problems, and that they can repay their loan with their salary.

Conclusion:

Banks play a central role in the transmission of monetary policy, one of the government's most important tools for achieving economic growth without inflation. Bankers play an essential role in society by protecting, investing, and lending money. Many play a direct role in helping clients' make some of the most important decisions of their lives, such as saving for college, purchasing homes, and planning for their business and retirement needs. They should be satisfied with their lives. Then only they can perform their work without any contravening versions.

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